

Reinforcement Learning Strategies for the Card Game 'Getaway' An Evaluation of Q-learning and SARSA

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Abstract

This paper investigates the application of model-free reinforcement learning algorithms to optimize an AI agent for the card game 'Getaway'. Specifically, we focus on two temporal difference learning methods: Q-learning for off-policy learning and SARSA for on-policy learning. We compare the policies derived from both algorithms, demonstrating that the Q-learning approach is more suited to the strategic requirements of 'Getaway'. Additionally, we introduce a novel adaptation to Q-learning that involves seeding initial Q-values for each state-action pair following extensive exploration. Our analysis details how this modification enhances the performance of the model, offering insights into its potential for broader applications in complex game environments.

Introduction

The objective of this research project is to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) agent capable of playing 'Getaway', a strategic card game similar to UNO, but utilizing a standard 52-card deck. The game requires a minimum of three players and can accommodate up to thirteen players using a single deck. In Getaway, each card's value corresponds to its face value: numbered cards (2-10) are valued at their respective numbers, J is valued at 11, Q at 12, K at 13, and A at 14, with the Ace being the highest valued card. Importantly, the value of a card is independent of its suit.

Gameplay begins with an equitable distribution of the deck among all players. The holder of the Ace of Spades initiates the game, which then proceeds in a clockwise direction. Gameplay dynamics allow the first player in each round to play any card from their hand, while subsequent players must follow the suit of the first card if able. If a player cannot follow suit, they may play any card, thereby terminating the round. The round concludes when all players have successfully followed suit. All cards played in a round are discarded at its conclusion, and the player who played the highest-value card commences the next round. Should a round terminate prematurely, the player to play the highest card collects all played cards into their hand. The game ends when a player depletes their hand, termed 'getting away', thereby winning the game.

The primary aim of this project is to engineer an AI agent that devises optimal strategies for Getaway using reinforcement learning techniques. For this study, the game environment is standardized to four players to facilitate controlled experimentation and analysis. The research employs two prominent reinforcement learning algorithms, Q-learning and SARSA, to evaluate and compare their effectiveness in this context. These algorithms were selected to provide insights into the performance distinctions between on-policy (SARSA) and off-policy (Q-learning) learning strategies under identical game conditions.

Background

Both SARSA and Q-Learning are types of Temporal Difference (TD) Learning algorithms. TD methods can learn directly from raw experience without a model of the environment's dynamics. These TD methods update estimates based in part on other learned estimates, without waiting for a final outcome (Sutton and Barto, p.119 2018.). Both these methods use a form of Generalized Policy Iteration, using the Bellman's equation.

Q-learning

Q-learning is a model-free reinforcement learning algorithm that operates effectively within Markovian environments. Developed by Watkins in 1989, this technique has been extensively applied in diverse fields such as robotics and strategic game playing, where it has proven to be both robust and flexible. Q-learning is characterized as an off-policy Temporal Difference (TD) control algorithm. The learned action-value function, Q , directly approximates q^* , the optimal action-value function, independent of the policy being followed.

Central to Q-learning is its method of determining the most advantageous action in any given state. It achieves this by maintaining a table of Q-values, where each value represents the expected sum of future rewards for a particular state-action pair, assuming subsequent actions adhere to an optimal policy. The algorithm for Q-learning is as follows:

Algorithm 1: Q-learning

```
1: Initialize  $Q(s, a)$ , for all  $s \in S^+, a \in A(s)$ , arbitrarily
   except that  $Q(\text{terminal}, \cdot)=0$ 
2: Let  $t = 0$ .
3: for Each episode : do
4:   Initialize  $S$ 
5:   for Each step of episode : do
6:     Choose  $A$  from  $S$  using policy derived from  $Q$  (e.g.,
        $\epsilon$ -greedy)
7:     Take action  $A$ , observe  $R, S'$ 
8:      $Q(S, A) \leftarrow Q(S, A) + \alpha[R + \gamma \max_a(Q(S', a) -$ 
        $Q(S, A))]$ 
9:      $S \leftarrow S'$ 
10:   end for until  $S$  is terminal
11: end for
```

where

α is the learning rate,
 R is the immediate Reward
 γ is the discount factor

SARSA

SARSA stands for State, Action, Reward, State, Action. It is a model-free reinforcement learning algorithm that enables agents to learn policy effectiveness directly through interactions with the environment. It follows an on-policy approach, where the learning process adheres strictly to the policy being evaluated and updated. While Q-learning can converge to an optimal policy irrespective of initial values, and policy, the convergence of SARSA to an optimal policy depends on the initial policy chosen to follow. Q-learning follows a more aggressive approach as it looks for an optimal action at every state, while SARSA looks for a safer approach. The algorithm for SARSA is explained in algorithm :2:

Algorithm 2: SARSA

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1: Initialize  $Q(s, a)$ , for all  $s \in S^+, a \in A(s)$ , arbitrarily
   except that  $Q(\text{terminal}, \cdot)=0$ 
2: Let  $t = 0$ .
3: for Each episode : do
4:   Initialize  $S$ 
5:   Choose  $A$  from  $S$  using policy derived from  $Q$  (e.g.,
        $\epsilon$ -greedy)
6:   for Each step of episode : do
7:     Choose  $A'$  from  $S'$  using policy derived from  $Q$ 
       (e.g.,  $\epsilon$ -greedy)
8:     Take action  $A$ , observe  $R, S'$ 
9:      $Q(S, A) \leftarrow Q(S, A) + \alpha[R + \gamma(Q(S', A') -$ 
        $Q(S, A))]$ 
10:     $S \leftarrow S'$ 
11:     $A \leftarrow A'$ 
12:   end for until  $S$  is terminal
13: end for
```

The major difference in these algorithms can be noted in assignment of $Q(S, A)$, Q learning uses the max of Q value of the next state across all possible actions of that state, while SARSA uses the Q-Value for the action derived from the policy.

Project Description

In order to use the Reinforcement learning algorithms, we need to formalize the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP). The definitions are as follows:

Environment: The game environment consists of 4 player agents, a random agent, that plays a random valid card from its hand at each turn. A greedy-min agent, that plays the smallest valid card from its hand at each turn A greedy-max agent, that plays the largest valid card from its hand at each turn The fourth player is the AI player that we are solving for.

The first 3 players are fixed, and the goal is to compare how the two reinforcement algorithms perform in optimizing the 4th player.

State: The state of a player is a set of cards in their hand. A standard deck consists of 52 cards, and all 4 players start with 13 cards each. This set of 13 cards is fixed and does not vary between games. Each player's state is 13 cards at the start of the game, and as the game proceeds, it can reduce or increase depending on the outcome of the round.

Action: An action is denoted by the card being played at each turn. If a player has a set of 10 cards, then 10 possible actions can be taken from that state.

Reward: The reward for winning a game is +100 and the reward for losing a game is -100. A reward of -1 is added for each action, motivating the agent to a faster win.

Learning Rate: The learning rate is $1/(\text{number of updates to the state})$.

Applying Reinforcement Learning

Player 1 is modeled to play as a Greedy Agent, who plays the largest card in their hand each turn. The initial distribution of cards for player 1 is A of Club, K of Diamond, Q of Heart, J of Spade, 10 of Club, 9 of Diamond, 8 of Heart, 7 of Spade, 6 of Club, 5 of Diamond, 4 of Heart, 3 of Spade, 2 of Club.

Player 2 is modeled to play as a Greedy-min agent, who plays the smallest card in their hand each turn. The initial distribution of cards for player 2 is A of Heart, K of Spade, Q of Club, J of Diamond, 10 of Heart, 9 of Spade, 8 of Club, 7 of Diamond, 6 of Heart, 5 of Spade, 4 of Club, 3 of Diamond, 2 of Heart.

Player 3 is modeled to play as a Random agent, who plays a random valid card in their hand each turn. The initial distribution of cards for player 3 is A of Diamond, K of Heart, Q of Spade, J of Club, 10 of Diamond, 9 of Heart, 8 of Spade, 7 of Club, 6 of Diamond, 5 of Heart, 4 of Spade, 3 of Club, 2 of Diamond,

Player 4 is the AI agent and receives the following cards as their initial hand. A of Spade, K of Club, Q of Diamond, J of Heart, 10 of Spade, 9 of Club, 8 of Diamond, 7 of Heart, 6 of Spade, 5 of Club, 4 of Diamond, 3 of Heart, 2 of Spade.

Only the state of the AI player is taken into account for modeling the game, and the states of other players are considered parts of the environment which is fixed, and not taken into account for calculation of Q values, or rewards.

From the initial distribution of cards, the player can play either of the 13 cards, making the action space to 13.

Q-learning

The AI agent incorporates an ϵ -greedy strategy with $\epsilon = 0.2$. This means that the agent takes a greedy policy, choosing the action that provides the max Q value 80% of the time, while choosing an action at random, 20% of the time. Following an ϵ -greedy policy with a value of $\epsilon > 0$ is necessary to explore the state space of the game. The act of choosing a random action is called the exploration part, and choosing the action with max Q value is the exploitation part.

$$A = \begin{cases} \operatorname{argmax}_a(Q(S, a)) & \text{with probability } (1 - \epsilon) \\ \text{random } a \in [a_1, a_2 \dots a_n] & \text{with probability } \epsilon \end{cases}$$

The Agent chooses an action 'A' following this strategy, and the Reward R is calculated by simulating the gameplay of other agents for a single round. Only one round is simulated and not the entire game as only the immediate reward of choosing an action should be considered.

The resulting state S' is the set of card in the hand minus the one card played. The Cardinality of initial state S is 13, and the resulting state S' is 12.

The Q value is then updated for the State action pair using a variant of Bellman's equation.

$$Q(S, A) \leftarrow Q(S, A) + \alpha[R + \gamma \max_a(Q(S', a) - Q(S, A))]$$

where

$$\alpha \text{ is the learning rate, } \alpha = \frac{1}{\text{number of updates to state S}}$$

$$\gamma \text{ is the discount factor, we consider } \textit{gamma} = 1$$

The current state is now set to S', and the same process is followed until a terminal state is reached. The Q(S,.) for a terminal state is 0, as there are no actions to be taken, and no subsequent state possible.

This ends a single episode. The same process is repeated several times until the values converge.

From the sum of the rewards graph, we can notice an increase in rewards as the learning progresses.

SARSA

The SARSA is an on-policy algorithm and requires a base policy to learn. Some options for the base policy for this game can be greedy-max, greedy-min, random, and an optimized greedy policy. The greedy-min, greedy-max, and random policies are similar to the other agents previously modeled. The optimized greedy policy is a policy where we play

Figure 1: Q-learning

the largest possible card smaller than the largest card in play. This policy is a conservative game strategy to avoid being the largest card and run the risk of accepting cards in a terminated round. To evaluate these 4 policies, the AI agent is replaced with each of the 4 policies one by one to assess their performance in the game environment playing against the 3 other agents, for 1000 episodes.

Table 1: Wins per 1000 episodes for different agent types

Agent Type	Wins per 1000 Episodes
Random	306
Greedy-Min	316
Greedy-Max	372
Greedy-Optimized	344

Since the Greedy-max strategy won the most number of games for p4, it is chosen as the base policy for SARSA.

The same ϵ -greedy strategy is followed for SARSA as well to take into account both exploration and exploitation.

$$A = \begin{cases} \pi(S) & \text{with probability } (1 - \epsilon) \\ \text{random } a \in [a_1, a_2 \dots a_n] & \text{with probability } \epsilon \end{cases}$$

where $\pi(S)$ denotes the policy for state 'S'.

After choosing action A using the above policy, the reward R is calculated by simulating one round of the game, and S' is determined. From S' we calculate A' using the same policy mentioned above. The value of state is updated using the equation

$$Q(S, A) \leftarrow Q(S, A) + \alpha[R + \gamma Q(S', A') - Q(S, A)]$$

where

$$\alpha \text{ is the learning rate, } \alpha = \frac{1}{\text{number of updates to state S}}$$

$$\gamma \text{ is the discount factor, we consider } \textit{gamma} = 1$$

The State S' is set as the current state, and the action to be taken is A' . Using these S' and A' we calculate the new Reward, next state, next action the update process is repeated until S is terminal.

Figure 2: SARSA

Comparing the win percentages and sum of rewards within the first 10,000 iterations of both Q-learning and SARSA show some interesting observations.

For Q-learning, there is a slight upward movement in the sum of rewards graph. This is because there is no base policy it is working upon and learns and improves the policy as the number of iterations progresses. This is also evident from the number of wins. The win percentage for SARSA cumulative of the first 10,000 games is 39.1%, and the win rate for Q-learning is 38.9%. During the first 10,000 episodes, the Sum of rewards, and the Win percentages have remained almost similar.

The major difference to note here is that even though both SARSA and Q-learning have similar win percentages, sum of rewards for SARSA is lower than that of Q-learning. The characteristic of SARSA is to take a conservative approach, and the lower sum of rewards shows that a conservative approach is not suitable for this game.

The probability of winning a game is $1/3$ of the probability of losing. The structure of the game if there is one good round for the agent, (causing a round to terminate against another player), the chances of winning increase, since the agent will have one less card than every other player for the rest of the game, leading to get away faster than the opponent and hence winning. Taking a conservative strategy means making sure the agent doesn't end up accepting more cards but does not increase the chances of winning, leading to a draw, where all players play off their cards in the same round.

After 1 million iterations of both SARSA and Q-learning, we can evaluate the performance of both reinforcement learning methods. The graph shows the comparison of wins for 10,000 games after 1 million iterations of training. The exploration part (ϵ) is set to 0 for these 10,000 iterations, to

Figure 3: Win comparison 1

benchmark the performance of the converged policies. the win percentage for q-learning.

From the graph, we can infer that Q-learning has improved further compared to SARSA. The win percentage for Q-learning in the 10,000 iterations was 46% compared to 39.7% for SARSA. From this, we can conclude that Q-learning suits this problem better, and was able to product better results compared to SARSA.

Figure 4: Win comparison 2

Experiments

Seeding Values for Q-learning

Even after 1 million iterations of both algorithms, the win percentage could not be improved to over 50%.

The total unique possible states for this game in an average case scenario ignoring some exceptional cases is 13 factorial. But since the agent can accept more cards during the game play, the actual number of unique states is much higher than this. In Q-learning, at each iteration, the agent only explores one action that it finds as optimal, and there is a chance that some states might have not been explored.

The total number of states that were visited after 1 million iterations was 18319.

To make sure we explore all possible states, we can simulate the game for all actions at each state to update all $Q(S,a)$ pairs at each state. This will increase the exploration, and these explored values can then be used as starting values for Q-learning.

The epsilon greedy policy for choosing the action is defined as :

$$A = \begin{cases} \mathit{argmax}_a (R(a) \text{ for } a \in A(S)) & \text{with probability } (1 - \epsilon) \\ \text{random } a \in [a_1, a_2 \dots a_n] & \text{with probability } \epsilon \end{cases}$$

The algorithm for exploring all states during a Q-learning episode is explained in algorithm: 3

Algorithm 3: Seeding values through Extensive Exploration

- 1: Initialize $Q(s, a)$, for all $s \in S^+, a \in A(s)$, arbitrarily except that $Q(\text{terminal}, \cdot) = 0$
 - 2: Let $t = 0$.
 - 3: **for** Each episode : **do**
 - 4: Initialize S
 - 5: **for** Each step of episode : **do**
 - 6: **for** Each action a in $A(S)$: **do**
 - 7: Calculate Reward $R(a)$.
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: Choose action A based on above ϵ -greedy policy
 - 10: $Q(S, A) \leftarrow Q(S, A) + \alpha [R + \max_a (Q(S', a) - Q(S, A))]$
 - 11: $S \leftarrow S'$
 - 12: **end for** until S is terminal
 - 13: **end for**
-

Using this algorithm to seed value into the Q-table, the total number of states visited improves from 18319 to 42686.

Running Q-learning algorithm by using these pre-seeded values, the win percentage increases to 58%.

The improvement in win win percentage is depicted in the graph below.

Figure 5: Win comparison 3

Removing stochasticity

The number of unique combinations of 13 cards the agent can get, from a deck of 52 cards is ${}^{52}C_{13}$. The number of possible actions at each state assuming optimal gameplay is (13!). This makes the total number of possible states =

$$\begin{aligned} &= {}^{52}C_{13} \times 13! \\ &= 635013559600 \times 6227020800 \\ &= 3954242643911239680000 = 3.95 \times 10^{21} \end{aligned}$$

Considering all the possibilities for the shuffled deck of cards introduces a tremendous amount of Stochasticity to the problem. To mitigate this, the initial distribution of cards was fixed. This brings down the possible states for our agent to $13!$ which is 6.2×10^9 . But this number comes down even further due to the effect of Afterstates.

The other source of stochasticity comes from the Random Agent player. Since one of the players in the environment uses a random strategy, the environment is stochastic. This stochasticity can be removed by replacing the Random player with the Greedy-optimal strategy that was evaluated as a consideration for SARSA's base policy.

The Random agent player in the environment is the only source of stochasticity since the initial set of cards is already

With the random player replaced with a deterministic agent, the environment is now deterministic. With this deterministic environment, the Qlearning agent is able to converge to an optimal policy within 100 iterations. The agent won 76 of the first 100 games, and after removing the exploration part ϵ after 100 iterations, the agent wins every single game henceforth.

Related Work

Beyond what has been explored in this paper, further experiments can be done using different sets of initial card distributions for this game. The initial card distribution was chosen arbitrarily while making sure the total value of cards is equal for each agent. Further investigation can be carried out using an unequal distribution of cards, and investigating the performance of q-learning and SARSA algorithms.

The initial card distribution was fixed to reduce the stochasticity and to restricting the size of Q-table. As an extension of Q-learning, the usage of Deep Q-learning needs to be explored.

Deep Q-learning is used in cases where the state space is massive, and using a Q-table is computationally complicated. Deep Q-Learning addresses these limitations by using a deep neural network to approximate the Q-value function, replacing the table with a function approximator. The neural network takes the state as input and outputs Q-values for all possible actions.

In Deep Q-Learning, a Deep Q-Network (DQN) replaces the Q-table. This network inputs the environment's state and outputs Q-values for all possible actions, handling vast and

complex input data. Training the DQN requires experience replay, where transitions (state, action, reward, next state) are stored in a buffer and randomly sampled to break the correlation between consecutive samples. The network is trained to minimize the difference between predicted Q-values and target Q-values derived from the Bellman equation.

To enhance stability, Deep Q-Learning employs techniques like a fixed target network, which separates the network used for generating target Q-values from the one updated continuously, reducing fluctuations in learning.

By using Deep Q Learning, a model can be trained to play the Getaway game with any starting card distribution.

In addition to Getaway game, the game UNO can also be modeled in a similar fashion, as these 2 games share a very play style.

Both Q-learning and SARSA are temporal difference learning algorithms. In addition to temporal difference learning, Monte Carlo Tree search can also be used to solve this problem. The other Temporal Difference learning methods that can also be used are Expected-SARSA and Double Q-learning.

Conclusion

This paper explored the usage of two model-free Temporal Difference algorithms. The Q-learning method is an off-policy TD learning algorithm, and SARSA is an on-policy TD learning algorithm. From applying these two algorithms, different strategies innately used by both of these algorithms could be noted. The Q-learning algorithm is greedy by design, and looks for the optimal action at every state. This pattern is riskier, as the agent stands a risk of getting penalized more often.

From the figure: 6, in a standard cliff walking problem, SARSA takes a safer route, resulting in a higher sum of rewards. This result is contrasting to the result observed in the game of Getaway. In a standard cliff walking problem, the agent avoids the risk of falling in the cliff by staying as far away as possible without any major downsides.

In the game of Getaway, a conservative strategy often results in losing the game or in a draw, and a risky play results in higher chances of winning. This is also supported by the data in Table 1, where a Greedy strategy outperforms the conservative Greedy-minimum strategy and the conservative greedy optimal strategy.

The benefit of taking risks resulting in higher rewards is proved by graphs from Figures 1 and 2.

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Figure 6: Sum of rewards for Cliff walking (Sutton and Barto, p.132 2018.)

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